

gases, and heated to 100°. The evolved gases during the concentration and conversion to CrO₃ was collected in a flask containing water. If Cr(III) oxidized as gaseous CrO₂Cl₂, it is hydrolyzed and Cr(VI) is determined iodometrically after boiling off the dissolved chlorine in the solution. Cr(IV) is also determined in the residual red mass. The analytical results are given in Table 1, which suggest

TABLE 1—DATA ON ANALYSIS OF CHROMIUM

(Cr ³⁺ + 3ClO ₃ ⁻) taken (m mole)	Found (m mo'e)		Molar ratio CrO ₃ /CrO ₂ Cl
	CrO ₂ Cl ₂	CrO ₃	
0.10	0.032	0.066	2.06
0.15	0.051	0.102	2.00
0.25	0.085	0.172	2.02

that 2/3 of Cr(III) is oxidized into CrO₃ and the remaining one-third to CrO₂Cl₂. The reaction scheme is given as

Slow evaporation of chromium(III) chlorate solution at room temperature, either keeping at open atmosphere or in a desiccator also resulted in the formation of CrO₃ after several days. Cr(VI) also formed in solution on boiling the acidified Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution. The fact that Cr(VI) formed after the removal of water from the chromium chlorate solution and only by boiling the acidified solution indicates that Cr(ClO₃)₃ is probably a low melting compound. However, all the attempted methods to isolate the solid, met with no success.

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Ligational Behaviour of *o*-Aminobenzoylhydrazine towards some Transition Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 19 November 1979,
accepted 25 December 1979

ACIDHYDRAZIDES and their derivatives have received considerable attention because of their potentiality as versatile coordinating agents^{1,2} as well as their antibacterial activity³⁻⁵. Extensive search of literature showed that no work has been done on the metal chelates of *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (LH), a potential tridentate ligand. We have also observed that this ligand molecule is capable of inhibiting the growth of some strains of tuberculosis mycobacteria⁶. In the present communication, we wish to make a preliminary report on the chelating behaviour of *o*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (LH) towards Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions. With Cu(II) salts, both mono- and bis-chelates have been isolated; whereas, the Co(II) and Ni(II) salts forms only 1 : 2 type complexes. In all these cases the ligand behaved as a neutral one. All the metal complexes have been prepared by reacting the metal salts with the ligand in warm aqueous-ethanol in 1 : 2 proportion, when microcrystalline complexes separated slowly. For the preparation of 1 : 1 type Cu(II) complexes, 1 : 1 molar ratio of the metal salt and the ligand was used. The analytical data and magnetic moment values of some of the representative complexes are given in Table 1.

The effective magnetic moment values for the complexes, Cu(LH)₂X₂.4H₂O (X = NO₃, $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄²⁻), fall in the range of distorted octahedral Cu(II) complexes⁷. On the other hand, the Cu(II) complexes of the formula Cu(LH)X₂.4H₂O (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄²⁻), exhibit subnormal magnetic moment values. The Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes show paramagnetism corresponding to two and three unpaired electrons respectively, in an octahedral environment^{8,9}. The electronic spectral data for all the complexes are also indicative of octahedral disposition of the donor sites around the metal ions.

The ligand molecule possess three potential donor sites namely, the carbonyl oxygen, the hydrazinic -NH₂ and the ring NH₂ groups. The i.r. spectrum of the ligand in KBr exhibits bands at 3420 cm⁻¹ and 3250 cm⁻¹. The first one may be assigned to the stretching vibration of the ring -NH₂¹⁰ and the second one to the superimposed stretching vibrations of -NH bands of the hydrazinic amino and imino groups. The lowering of the band at 3250 cm⁻¹ by 10-50 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes is suggestive of hydrazinic -NH₂ - coordination to the metal ions. The ligand shows a strong absorption band at 1655 cm⁻¹ (amide I band), which

*For communication.

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Analysis%			μ_{eff} B.M. 300°K
		Metal	Nitrogen	Anion	
Co(LH) ₂ Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Pink	11.52 (11.69)	16.80 (16.67)	13.95 (14.07)	5.00
Co(LH) ₂ Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Flesh Coloured	9.86 (9.94)	14.05 (14.17)	26.62 (26.96)	4.80
Co(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Pinkish White	10.48 (10.58)	19.97 (20.10)	—	4.77
Co(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Pinkish White	11.05 (11.14)	15.69 (15.88)	18.20 (18.14)	4.83
Ni(LH) ₂ Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	11.58 (11.65)	16.75 (16.67)	13.95 (14.07)	4.00
Ni(LH) ₂ Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	9.78 (9.90)	13.99 (14.17)	26.78 (26.97)	3.01
Ni(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Bluish Grey	10.48 (10.54)	20.00 (20.11)	—	2.93
Ni(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Sky blue	10.98 (11.10)	15.95 (15.88)	18.05 (18.15)	2.91
Cu(LH)Cl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	17.60 (17.75)	11.58 (11.75)	19.61 (19.84)	1.37
Cu(LH)Br ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Dirty Green	14.07 (14.21)	9.52 (9.41)	35.53 (35.81)	1.48
Cu(LH)(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light blue	15.33 (15.45)	17.18 (17.05)	—	1.44
Cu(LH)SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Greenish blue	16.48 (16.59)	10.78 (10.98)	24.87 (25.10)	1.43
Cu(LH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	11.20 (11.30)	19.84 (19.94)	—	1.80
Cu(LH) ₂ SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Light Green	11.77 (11.89)	15.58 (15.74)	16.78 (17.03)	1.83

* Figures in the parenthesis represent the calculated values.

suffers a depression of 20-55 cm⁻¹ in the chelated species indicating the participation of the carbonyl group in bonding to the metal ion through its oxygen atom. As is observed here, bonding from the carbonyl oxygen and the terminal -NH₂ of the acid hydrazides is a well established fact^{1,2}.

In view of the subnormal magnetic moment values of the 1 : 1 Cu(II) complexes, the following dimeric formulation (Fig. 1), in which the carbonyl group act as a bridge between two Cu(II) centres, is proposed :

Fig. 1.

Cryomagnetic studies on the 1 : 1 Cu(II) complexes are being done and will be reported soon.

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A Study of Vanadyl(IV) Complex of Fluorescein—Thermal Studies of Amine Adducts. Part-VII.

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Manuscript received 27 November 1979, accepted 25 December 1979

DETAILED studies on complexes of fluorescein including that of vanadyl⁵, have already been reported¹⁻⁵. The vanadyl ion having a strong and dominant axial field and four ligand moieties

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